

Chronicle of a Foretold Death — Severe Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension in Pregnancy Secondary to an Unspecified Maternal Cyanotic Congenital Heart Disease.” Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Pregnancy is a period during which significant physiological changes occur in all organs and systems of a woman’s body. The cardiovascular system is no exception; it undergoes some of the most relevant changes and requires a complex, gradual readaptation. Healthy pregnant women can tolerate these changes, but in women with heart disease this can lead to a marked increase in maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality— in some cases exceeding 50%. Below we describe the case of an obstetric patient with pulmonary arterial hypertension secondary to a cyanotic congenital heart disease: its detection, prenatal follow-up, management, clinical course, treatment, and outcome.

Objective: To report the case of an obstetric patient with an unspecified cyanotic congenital heart disease complicated by pulmonary arterial hypertension. To describe its detection, prenatal care, clinical course, and maternal–fetal outcome developed at the General Hospital of Cancun.

Keywords: Pulmonary arterial hypertension, Heart failure, Cyanotic congenital heart disease, Cardiovascular complication, Pregnancy.

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INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade there has been a significant decrease in maternal mortality worldwide, largely due to the implementation of improvements in obstetric care and the timely detection of acute pregnancy complications. These improvements have shifted the epidemiologic profile of maternal death, reducing direct causes—those directly related to pregnancy such as hemorrhage and preeclampsia—and allowing greater recognition of indirect causes. The latter include preexisting or pregnancy-acquired medical conditions not caused by pregnancy itself but exacerbated by the physiological changes of the gravid state, as is the case with all cardiopathies. [3]

Heart disease is considered the most important non-obstetric cause of maternal death during pregnancy. [4] The global incidence of pulmonary arterial hypertension is 15 cases per million. [10] According to natural history studies, approximately 30% of children born with inherited heart disease who do not undergo surgical repair will develop pulmonary vascular disease. [2] During pregnancy, the most important hemodynamic changes are increased blood volume and heart rate, increased oxygen consumption, reduced peripheral vascular resistance, and a procoagulant state. [5] Pulmonary arterial hypertension is a complex pathophysiological and hemodynamic disorder that can be secondary to multiple causes; the most common is left heart disease (up to 78.3%), whose most severe complication is

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Eisenmenger syndrome. [4] Pulmonary arterial hypertension is characterized by an increase in pressure in the pulmonary arteries that can lead to right ventricular failure and even death if adequate treatment is not provided.

The classification currently most accepted for Pulmonary Hypertension, including pulmonary arterial hypertension addressed here, is that established by the international ESC/ERS 2022 guidelines on the diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary hypertension.

The criteria used to assess a patient with pulmonary arterial hypertension to determine disease severity are classified according to clinical, hemodynamic, and echocardiographic conditions. Clinically, exertional dyspnea is the principal symptom raising diagnostic suspicion. Regardless of the underlying etiology, pulmonary arterial hypertension leads to pressure overload and right ventricular dysfunction, which can be detected by echocardiography.

The natural history of pulmonary arterial hypertension during pregnancy is associated with unpredictable risks, and pregnancy itself accelerates the progression of pulmonary arterial hypertension; therefore, all women who wish to become pregnant should plan the pregnancy and receive multidisciplinary counseling about risks and adverse events related to all stages of pregnancy. It generally carries a mortality of 30% to 56%, with the puerperium being the critical and most severe period for these patients. [11]

PRESENTATION OF THE CASE

Female patient, 40 years old, who presented to her primary care center to enroll in the prenatal control program. An abdominal obstetric ultrasound reported a pregnancy of 14.2 weeks' gestation by composite anthropometry. The patient was referred to the General Hospital of Cancun with a diagnosis of 15.2 weeks' gestation by date of last menstrual period, because this was considered a high-risk pregnancy according to unspecified risk factors.

The patient attended the high-risk obstetric clinic (first visit) at the Gynecology and Obstetrics Department of the General Hospital of Cancun five weeks later. Non-pathologic history:

native of Guatemala, resident of Cancun, Quintana Roo, domestic worker, single, completed up to secondary school, evangelical. Main relevant past medical history: unspecified congenital heart disease diagnosed at age 30, without treatment or medical follow-up. Allergic to acetylsalicylic acid. No prior surgeries. Gynecologic–obstetric history: first pregnancy; menarche at 14 years; regular 30-day cycles with 5-day menses; non-debilitating dysmenorrhea; sexual debut at 15 years; three sexual partners; no contraceptive use; Pap smear never performed. Last menstrual period: January 10, 2023. Estimated date of delivery: October 17, 2023. On directed history, the patient reported exertional dyspnea on moderate effort (climbing two flights of stairs or attempting to run), NYHA class II, denying other associated symptoms and denying symptoms suggestive of infection or risk of pregnancy loss such as bleeding or pain.

On physical examination, the patient was in good general condition, cooperative, and oriented in three spheres. Weight 34.5 kg, height 135 cm. Neck without jugular venous distention. Heart sounds regular. Lungs clear and well ventilated. Abdomen protuberant due to gravid uterus; fundal height 23 cm. Single fetus with fetal heart rate 144 beats per minute. Vaginal examination deferred. Lower limbs: distal cyanosis of the toes; left hand with clubbed-appearing fingers; agenesis of the right hand with only a digital stump.

Transthoracic echocardiogram: borderline left ventricular systolic function, LVEF 50%; dilated right ventricle with signs of pressure and volume overload; moderate tricuspid regurgitation; mild aortic regurgitation; moderate pulmonary regurgitation with pulmonary artery dilation; high probability of pulmonary hypertension. Estimated systolic pulmonary artery pressure (sPAP) 95.5 mmHg.

Hospital admission was indicated to continue diagnostic workup and establish medical treatment. The patient declined immediate hospitalization for personal reasons and was admitted one week later with a diagnosis of 22.3 weeks' gestation by second-trimester ultrasound and congenital heart disease under evaluation.

Imagen 1. The electrocardiogram shows sinus rhythm; heart rate 83 bpm; PR interval 0.16 s; incomplete right bundle branch block; QRS duration 0.98 s; rightward axis deviation; lead I with P wave 3 mV, suggestive of right atrial enlargement.

Chronicle of a Foretold Death — Severe Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension in Pregnancy Secondary to an Unspecified Maternal Cyanotic Congenital Heart Disease.” Case Report

During hospitalization, the Cardiology service evaluated the patient, confirmed severe pulmonary arterial hypertension with right-sided chamber dilatation, and recommended transfer to a tertiary care center for continued clinical management and resolution of the pregnancy. The Gynecology-Obstetrics team explained the severity, risks, and potential consequences of continuing the pregnancy, offered pregnancy termination and transfer to tertiary care as medical management; the patient declined and requested voluntary discharge.

Two months after discharge the patient attended a follow-up in the High-Risk Obstetrics outpatient clinic with a gestational age of 32.2 weeks by LMP, reporting increased dyspnea on mild-to-moderate exertion and intermittent lower-limb edema that resolved spontaneously. Physical examination: pulmonary auscultation with a murmur at the pulmonary focus; abdomen distended due to gravid uterus with fundal height 25 cm; single fetus, cephalic presentation, longitudinal lie, dorsum to the left; fetal heart rate 145 bpm; distal cyanosis of upper and lower extremities and mild perioral cyanosis. She presented an obstetric ultrasound reporting 25.5 weeks' gestation and posterior fundal placenta with Grannum grade II maturation. Given suspected intrauterine growth restriction and progression of the underlying condition, hospital admission was indicated for multidisciplinary management and transfer to tertiary care; the patient again declined admission despite high maternal and fetal complication risk.

She was taken to the operating room and a Red Code was activated. Delivery was performed via midline abdominal cesarean section under epidural blockade in an estimated time of 35 minutes. Intraoperative blood loss was estimated at 500 ml; 350 ml of Hartmann's solution was administered. A male neonate was delivered at 13:55 h, estimated fetal weight 1,730 g, length 43 cm, Apgar 6/8, Capurro 35 weeks' gestation; amniotic fluid was meconium-stained. The neonate was admitted to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit. Surgical sterilization was performed. After completion of the procedure the patient was transferred to the Adult Intensive Care Unit. She required no vasopressors and no central access at arrival. Vital signs: blood pressure 132/70 mmHg (MAP 86 mmHg), HR 100 bpm, RR 20/min, SpO₂ 65% on supplemental oxygen at 8 l/min.

Eight hours post operated during the night shift, laboratory tests showed: total bilirubin 2.13 mg/dL, direct bilirubin 0.73 mg/dL, indirect bilirubin 1.40 mg/dL; AST 622 U/L, ALT 322 U/L; lactate dehydrogenase 1,247 U/L; glucose 136 mg/dL; urea 25.9 mg/dL; serum creatinine 1.0 mg/dL; D-dimer 3,155.52 ng/mL. Arterial blood gas: pH 6.9, pCO₂ 32 mmHg, pO₂ 45.2 mmHg, lactate 10 mmol/L, HCO₃⁻ 7.9 mmol/L. A central venous catheter was placed for fluid management.

Twenty-four hours after surgery Cardiology assessed the patient and reported right-sided heart failure secondary to

right-chamber dilatation with findings consistent with pulmonary arterial hypertension. During the subsequent night, she developed hemodynamic deterioration requiring high-dose vasopressor support, with non-perfusion MAP and SpO₂ 72%. Telemetry showed an isoelectric line; carotid pulse was absent. Advanced cardiac life support was performed for five cycles without return of spontaneous circulation. Cause of death was declared as heart failure secondary to cyanotic congenital heart disease.

DISCUSSION

Currently, in both developed and developing countries, advances in medical and surgical management have made it possible for more than 85% of children with congenital heart disease to survive into adulthood, and approximately half of this cohort are women of reproductive age, making these cases increasingly common. [3]

The increase in plasma volume of 30–50% overall is an adaptive process that occurs gradually according to fetal requirements, beginning around the sixth week, peaking at 20–24 weeks, and persisting until delivery. Cardiac output increases in parallel with plasma volume, although it is not constant and varies with maternal position; in the supine position the uterus compresses the vena cava, reducing venous return and thus cardiac output.

Ventricular diameters increase slightly but generally remain within normal limits. Left ventricular contractility is mildly depressed, yet ejection fraction is preserved because of changes in preload and afterload. Transvalvular velocities increase due to the hyperdynamic state, and mild valvular regurgitation is common. Aortic root diameter also increases during pregnancy. [3] These changes are normal in a healthy woman; however, as described in the reported case—where structural and functional abnormalities indicative of chronic deterioration secondary to an unspecified cyanotic congenital heart disease were found—these adaptations were not tolerated during the third trimester.

Finally, the third most relevant physiological change—and a reason pregnancy can be sustained in some patients with pulmonary arterial hypertension—is the reduction in systemic vascular resistance of about 30%. Pulmonary pressures remain normal in healthy pregnancies due to a reduction in pulmonary vascular resistance that compensates for increased pulmonary blood flow. However, when right ventricular dysfunction and impaired left ventricular ejection are present, as in the reported case, compensation is inadequate, explaining the clinical manifestations seen in pregnant patients with this condition.

Pulmonary arterial hypertension is defined as a mean pulmonary arterial pressure >20 mmHg at rest measured by invasive right-heart catheterization, combined with a pulmonary vascular resistance >2 Wood units and a pulmonary artery wedge pressure ≤15 mmHg. [10]

Chronicle of a Foretold Death — Severe Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension in Pregnancy Secondary to an Unspecified Maternal Cyanotic Congenital Heart Disease.” Case Report

The ESC/ERS 2022 guideline on the diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary hypertension classifies pulmonary hypertension with the aim of grouping clinical entities by pathophysiologic mechanism. It divides pulmonary hypertension into five main groups: 1) Pulmonary arterial hypertension; 2) Pulmonary hypertension due to left heart disease; 3) Pulmonary hypertension due to lung disease and/or hypoxia; 4) Pulmonary hypertension due to pulmonary artery obstructions; and 5) Pulmonary hypertension of unclear or multifactorial mechanism. [13]

Typical presentation of pulmonary arterial hypertension includes dyspnea (60%), fatigue (19%), syncope (8%), chest pain (7%), palpitations (5%), and peripheral edema (3%). Clinical course is variable, but without treatment progressive deterioration occurs with a life expectancy of approximately 2.8 years after diagnosis; this correlates with the symptoms presented by the patient in the reported case. Functional capacity closely correlates with poor prognosis. [12] Dyspnea results from decreased cardiac output together with ventilation–perfusion mismatch. Other signs and symptoms include peripheral cyanosis, fatigue, and edema.

Echocardiography is a diagnostic tool across all groups and is especially useful in pulmonary hypertension associated with left heart disease and congenital heart disease, as in this case. A comprehensive echocardiographic assessment includes estimation of systolic pulmonary artery pressure (sPAP), peak tricuspid regurgitation velocity (TRV), basal right and left ventricular diameters, and pulmonary artery diameter—parameters that were abnormal in the presented case. Left ventricular systolic dysfunction predisposes to pulmonary hypertension.

An indirect diagnostic resource suggesting pulmonary arterial hypertension is the electrocardiogram, which may show suggestive findings—several of which were evident in the reported case—including P wave >0.25 mV in lead II, right axis deviation, signs of right ventricular hypertrophy, complete or incomplete right bundle branch block, and prolonged corrected QT interval.

Guidelines recommend that women of reproductive age with pulmonary arterial hypertension receive counseling on contraception and that pregnancy termination be considered early (therapeutic abortion) when pregnancy occurs; this recommendation raises important moral considerations. [6] The first measure considered in this case was pregnancy termination due to the high associated maternal mortality; however, it should be noted that the patient’s decisions and autonomy were respected despite the prognosis, timely diagnosis, and comprehensive specialist counseling. Factors associated with poor prognosis in pregnancy include right ventricular hypertrophy, low cardiac index, elevated right atrial pressure, and increased pulmonary vascular resistance. [12]

During labor, women with this disease face higher risk of complications because the physiological demands of labor

and the aforementioned alterations can precipitate symptomatic exacerbation, with serious adverse consequences for both mother and fetus. As occurred in the reported case, clinical deterioration and symptomatic urgency developed during labor, necessitating abdominal delivery to preserve the life of the mother–fetus dyad. Currently, cesarean delivery is often preferred over vaginal delivery because it allows more controlled management. [10]

Atrial and ventricular diameters and volumes of both left and right chambers increase, while ventricular function is generally preserved. Blood pressure and cardiac output increase during labor. After delivery, uterine contraction causes cardiac output to fall rapidly to 15–25% above baseline. Over the following 3–4 weeks, cardiac output gradually decreases, reaching pregestational levels by approximately six weeks postpartum. These are the normal gradual changes in a healthy woman; however, the same changes are poorly tolerated in patients with pulmonary arterial hypertension and, as in the presented case, can precipitate right heart failure and death. The highest risk of complications occurs in the peripartum period, with peak mortality between postpartum days 2 and 9. Death most commonly results from irreversible right ventricular failure or arrhythmia. [3] This sequence was consistent with the disease course observed in the reported case despite medical intervention.

CONCLUSION

The management of pregnant patients with previously undiagnosed cyanotic heart disease who develop secondary pulmonary arterial hypertension represents a significant clinical challenge due to the complexity of the physiological changes induced by pregnancy. Pulmonary hypertension, as a complication of congenital heart disease, can lead to severe hemodynamic decompensation, placing both maternal and fetal health at risk. This case highlights the importance of early identification of cardiovascular disease in women of childbearing age, as well as the need for a multidisciplinary approach involving cardiologists, obstetricians, and other specialists to ensure timely and appropriate management. Although advances in maternal care have reduced direct maternal mortality, cardiovascular diseases remain one of the leading indirect causes of severe complications during pregnancy. Early diagnosis and individualized, coordinated management are essential to improve patient prognosis, prevent complications, and optimize maternal–fetal outcomes.

All women of childbearing age with pulmonary arterial hypertension should be adequately informed about the risks associated with pregnancy, particularly regarding maternal mortality. This counseling should be provided and reinforced systematically at every clinical encounter, emphasizing that pregnancy in this condition is potentially fatal and therefore constitutes a contraindication. The case presented clearly

Chronicle of a Foretold Death — Severe Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension in Pregnancy Secondary to an Unspecified Maternal Cyanotic Congenital Heart Disease.” Case Report

illustrates the unfavorable course of a patient with an unspecified cyanotic congenital heart disease and severe pulmonary arterial hypertension, who experienced a predictable outcome consistent with the natural history of the disease after disregarding medical recommendations and counseling, ultimately resulting in maternal death secondary to right heart failure.

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